

Tonolli Memorial Awards

Siecha Lakes Colombia. Photo by Carlos Rivera

Colombia

Benthic macroinvertebrate food webs are mainly sustained by autotrophic resources in tropical first-order forest streams

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Food webs that are based on detritus are usually shorter, less size-structured, and with a lower degree of omnivory than food webs based on autotrophic resources (Potapov *et al.*, 2019). In tropical first-order streams, the availability of basal resources changes with seasonality and its effect on the hydrology of streams. We aimed to establish whether the benthic macroinvertebrate food web in two tropical first-order forest streams relies on autotrophic or detrital food resources on a seasonal basis (rainy and dry seasons).

We evaluated the assimilation of autotrophic (benthic algae) and detrital (leaf litter) food resources through carbon and nitrogen stable isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) in two tropical first-order forest streams, José and Mario, in the Lacandona rainforest, in Chiapas, Mexico (Fig. 1). We included the biomass of macroinvertebrates sustained by each trophic pathway and the food web structure, i.e., trophic position, size structure, and degree of omnivory.

The largest available biomass of food resources (99%) in both streams and seasons was detritus, which increased in the dry season compared to the rainy season. Detrital biomass likely increased in the dry season due to a leaf drop peak associated with water stress of the riparian trees and low flow in the channel that increased litter retention (Tonin *et al.*, 2017). Detritus showed high C:N values (18.6–30.8) and depleted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig. 2).

Autotrophic food resources represented 1% of the biomass of potential food resources. Their biomass was higher in the dry season than in the rainy season. In tropical streams, the biomass of benthic primary producers increases in the dry season when water discharge and turbidity

Fig. 1: A. Location of the study streams. B. José stream (left) and Mario stream (right). Modified from Cortés-Guzmán *et al.* 2022b.

decrease (Branco *et al.*, 2017). Autotrophic food resources showed low C:N values (2.8–11.5) and enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values (Fig. 2).

The contribution of the autotrophic pathway (67%) to the macroinvertebrate biomass was higher than the detrital pathway (33%) in the José stream, particularly in the dry season. In contrast, the contribution of the detrital pathway did not differ between seasons. The contributions of the autotrophic (53%) and detrital (47%) pathways did not differ in the Mario stream. Even when their availability is limited, high selectivity for algae is probably associated with algae's higher

nutritional value compared to the recalcitrant components of leaf litter (Schmidt *et al.*, 2017).

The trophic structure was characterized by a higher maximum trophic position in the dry season in both streams. Isotopic enrichment in the dry season could be related to an increase in light penetration (Lau *et al.*, 2009). In both streams and seasons, between 52 and 79% of taxa were classified as omnivorous, while between 21 and 48% of taxa occurred at discrete trophic positions. Omnivory is widespread in tropical streams, likely as an adaptive response to the temporal variability of food resources

relative to the life span of the organisms (Digel *et al.*, 2011). We did not find a correlation between the macroinvertebrate trophic position and body mass (body mass [Ln (mg C) + 1] = 0.918 + 0.3 * trophic position, $r^2 = 0.01$, $p = 0.098$). Some taxa, such as crustaceans or gastropods, had large body mass but occupied an intermediate trophic position, which resulted in a poorly developed food web size structure.

We concluded that the autotrophic pathway played an important role in the macroinvertebrate food web in tropical streams, even when their availability was limited. Its relative importance varied with seasonality (Cortés Guzmán *et al.* 2022a;b).

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Fig. 2: Distribution of the isotopic signature of the macroinvertebrates and basal resources in the José and Mario streams, México in the rainy and dry seasons. (TP: average values of trophic positions 2, 3, and 4).

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NEWS FROM MEMBERS

Brazilian SIL member Hugo Sarmento shares the following news:

We had a big fire on the shores of the Broa reservoir, a lake we have been following long-term, and we intensified our sampling efforts to study the effects of forest fires on this aquatic ecosystem. More info at: <https://fb.watch/8y-jFr4r17/>

The Tara schooner is in Brazil, part of the AtlantECO project (H2020). Although this project is mainly about marine science, we did some sampling in the Amazon River and the Amazon plume. Check out this video: <https://youtu.be/byORIMJfCaw>